

Scorpion external morphology glossary

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Introduction

A general guide and dictionary of extant scorpion morphological terminologies based mostly on conventional definitions.

Abbreviations:

- a.k.a., also known as.
 - *adj.*, adjective form.
 - *pl.*, plural form.
 - L., Latin.
 - Gr., Greek.
 - Sp., Spanish
 - Fr., French.
 - En., English.
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Anatomical orientation

[Defined by the natural position of the animal (median ocelli directed upwards).]

1. Anterior & posterior

- Applied to the trunk; (1) anterior: the carapacial margin adjacent to the chelicerae; (2) posterior: the tip of the telson.
- Aligning the anterior and posterior ends establishes the somatic axis.

2. Proximal & distal

- Applied to the appendages, which extend outward from the trunk.
- Locations (including surfaces) closer to the trunk are termed “proximal”, while those further away are termed “distal”.
- Aligning the proximal and distal ends establishes the segmental axis.

3. Basal & terminal

- Applied to the appendages, representing special cases of “proximal” and “distal”.
- The most proximal location of the segment is termed “basal”, and the most distal location is termed “terminal”.

4. Dorsal & ventral

- **Trunk:** (1) dorsal surface of prosoma: carapace; (2) dorsal surface of mesosoma: tergites; (3) dorsal surface of metasoma: the upper plane parallel to the horizon when the metasoma is placed flat and straightened; (4) dorsal surface of telson: the plane which tapers and curves downwards posteriorly (into an aculeus); and vice versa for the ventral surface (metasomal ventral surface may include two to three sectional planes divided by carinae when they are present).
- **Appendages:** (1) dorsal surface of chelicera: the large, convex, non-setose plane; (2) dorsal surfaces of pedipalp femur and patella: the upper largest plane (that of patella may include two to three sectional planes divided by carinae when they are present); (3) dorsal surface of pedipalp chela: applicable only when the chela is carinate and defined similarly to other segments when the condylar axis is leveled; (4) dorsal margin of pedipalp movable finger: the dentate edge; (4) dorsal surface of leg segment: the upper narrow plane when the leg is positioned with its unguis facing downward; and vice versa for the ventral surface (ventral margin of pedipalp fixed finger: the dentate edge).

5. Lateral & medial

- Applied to the trunk; lateral surfaces of the carapace and tergites are continuous with their dorsal surfaces without evident boundaries; lateral surface of the metasoma corresponds to all large surfaces except the dorsal and ventral ones; lateral surface of the telson is continuous with its ventral surface without evident boundaries. Locations on or closer to the somatic axis or centroid are termed medial; i.e., medial is defined as between the bilateral boundaries.

5.1 Prolateral & retrolateral:

- Applied to the appendages, mainly for leg segments, and pedipalp patella and femur; prolateral surface of leg segments corresponds to the largest visible plane in dorsal view, while retrolateral surface corresponds to largest visible plane in ventral view; prolateral surface of patella and femur corresponds to the anterior plane when they are aligned perpendicular to the somatic axis, while retrolateral surface corresponds to the posterior plane.

6. External (outer) & internal (inner)

- Usage hereby restricted to locations on the body surface.
 - When applied to the pedipalp chela, external surface faces away from the chelal axis when aligned parallel to the somatic axis, while internal surface faces towards it.
 - When applied to the pedipalp patella and femur, internal and external surfaces are synonymous with prolateral and retrolateral surfaces respectively.
 - When used for other cases, a location is termed “external” if it is away from the center (on the somatic axis) of the scorpion, and “internal” if it is towards the center. When the location is on a segment, the segmental axis should be parallel with the somatic axis (particularly when applied to the pedipalp, it should be straightened forwardly in advance).
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Trunk

I. Prosoma (*pl.* prosomas, prosomata; *adj.* prosomal)

[L. *pro-*, “front”; Gr. *σῶμα* (*sōma*), “body”]

a.k.a. Cephalothorax (i.e., head + chest).

- A compact and compound segment bearing all appendages.
- Dorsally covered by the carapace; ventrally constituted by coxapophyses, coxae and sternum.

1. Carapace (*pl.* carapace; *adj.* carapacial):

[Sp. *carapacho*, “shell”]

a.k.a. Prosomal shield.

- Colloquially known as the “head” of the scorpion; upper half of the prosoma.
- A cuticular shield bearing eyes, setae and various morphosculptures.

1.1. Ocellus (*pl.* ocelli; *adj.* ocellar, ocular):

[L. *ocellus*, diminutive of *oculus*, “eye”]

a.k.a. Eye.

- Two types of visual organs (median and lateral ocelli), differing in structure and function (detailed in Hjelle (1990)).
- Both or either may be absent in some troglomorphic species.

(1) Median ocellus:

- Occurs in a pair when present; situated closely and symmetrically to the carapacial axis.
- Varies in size and position (including interocular distance) along the carapacial axis, but never present on margins.
- Larger than the lateral ocellus; specialized for acuity and spatial discrimination (can form low-resolution images).

(2) Lateral ocellus:

- Occurs in pairs when present; situated on the anterolateral margin of carapace.
- Varies in size, number (0~5 at one side; few taxa with 4 accessory ocelli) and position (4th ocellus occurs at 3 positions).
- Smaller than the median ocellus, without a vitreous body and focusing lens; specialized for minor variations in brightness.

(3) Eyespot:

- An understudied structure that is typically white to yellow and glabrous, situated posteroventral or ventral to the lateral ocelli and varies in shape.
- Does not possess lens and thus serves no visual function, but can detect light.
- Common in buthids and chaerilids; also observed in caraboctonids, chactids, hadrurids, troglotayosicids, and vaejovids.

2. Coxapophysis (*pl.* coxapophyses):

[“coxa” + “apophysis”; see below]

a.k.a. Maxillary lobe; maxillary process; mesal lobes; coxal endites.

- Coxapophyses I–II constitute the ventral side of the preoral concavity.
- 1st coxapophysis: a semi-crescent-shaped structure posterior to the ipsilateral pedipalp coxa and anterior to the leg I coxa.
- 2nd coxapophysis: a straight-back knife-shaped structure flanked by the ipsilateral 1st coxapophysis and leg I–II coxae.
- Both coxapophyses appear in pairs and are symmetrical to the somatic axis.
- The 1st coxapophysis is separated from the 2nd by a narrow suture; the 2nd coxapophysis pair is separated by a deep suture.
- The 1st coxapophysis and its ipsilateral leg I coxa are delineated by a wider, shallow furrow; it is essentially a result of oblique partitioning of leg I coxa.
- The 2nd coxapophysis and its ipsilateral leg II coxa are delineated by a narrow, shallower suture; it is essentially a result of vertical extension of leg II coxa between leg I coxae.

3. Coxa (*pl.* coxae; *adj.* coxal):

[L. *coxa*, “hip”]

- Coxae are segments of appendages (pedipalps and legs) but they are listed here as they largely constitute the ventral surface of prosoma.

3.1. Pedipalp coxa:

- A pair of relatively large, movable segments that constitute the lateral sides of the preoral concavity.
- Envelopes the ipsilateral pairs of coxapophyses, leg I coxa and leg I trochanter anteriorly.
- Curves downward anteriorly, converges towards the somatic axis, ends in a granular internal margin.

3.2 Leg coxa:

- Four pairs of rigid and immobile segments, each bearing a leg on the concave external margin.
- Ventrally flattened and smooth, and may be marginally granulated, crenulated or serrated.
- Coxae I–IV are conspicuously different in shape and size, with coxa I often being small and subtriangular, coxa II being trapezoid, and coxae III–III tapering towards the internal centroid (sternum), appearing subtriangular.
- Coxa IV is always the longest and most slender segment, which bounds the anterolateral part of ventral mesosoma.
- Coxae I and II are separated by a short, deep depression; coxae II and III are separated by a deeper gap; coxae III and IV are only delineated by a fine suture.
- Coxa I is isolated from its contralateral coxa by the 2nd coxapophysis; coxa II is divided from its contralateral coxa by the extreme apex of sternum; coxae II and III are separated from their contralateral coxae by the sternum.

4. Sternum (*pl.* sterna; *adj.* sternal):

[Gr. στήρνον (stérnon), “breast, chest”]

Anatomical equivalence: fused ventral of somites VII and VIII.

- A small sclerotized plate located in the ventral center of prosoma; pentagonal (primitive character state), sub-triangular or transverse in shape (shapes are interspecifically and ontogenetically variable).
- Posterior to leg II coxae, flanked by leg III–IV coxae, and anterior to genital operculum.
- Extracorporeal aspects of sternum characterized by a few terms (Soleglad & Fet, 2003a: 9): apex, apical button, apical depression, concave region, median furrow, posterior depression, posterior emargination, lateral lobes, and outer ridge.
- Categorized into Type 1 and Type 2 (Soleglad & Fet, 2003a); (1) Type 1: five-sided, always with a posterior depression that does not bisect the posterior margin; (2) Type 2: six-sided, always with posterior emargination and lateral lobes.

II. Opisthosoma (*pl.* opisthosomas, opisthosomata; *adj.* opisthosomal)

[Gr. ὀπισθεν (ópisthen), “behind”; Gr. σῶμα (sôma), “body”]

a.k.a. Abdomen.

- 12 segments consisting of *mesosoma* (7 segments) and *metasoma* (5 segments).

- A linguistic note: “opisthosoma” and “metasoma” are conventionally translated as “末体” (terminal body) and “后体” (rear body) in Chinese, but from both etymological and anatomical perspectives, a reverse of the translation is deemed more appropriate. Etymologically, “metasoma” should be translated as “从体” or “随体” (succeeding body).

III. Mesosoma (*pl.* mesosomas; *adj.* mesosomal)

[Gr. μέσος (mésos), “middle”; Gr. σῶμα (sôma), “body”]

a.k.a. Preabdomen.

Anatomical equivalence: somites X–XVI = mesosomal segments I–VII.

- Colloquially known as the “main body” of the scorpion.
- Connecting with the prosoma anteriorly and metasoma posteriorly.
- Bearing all tergites and sternites on a membrane and enclosing the majority of the visceral organs.
- Limited flexibility, mainly able to arch upwardly and laterally to a finite extent.

1. Tergite (*pl.* tergites; *adj.* tergal):

[L. *tergum*, *tergus*, “back(side)”]

Anatomical equivalence: dorsal of somites X–XVI = dorsal of mesosomal segments I–VII = tergites I–VII.

- Seven sclerotized plates, each divided into a pretergite and a posttergite by a ridged, undulate anterior edge (slightly extended to the anterolateral margin) of the latter.
- The ridged edge is typically finely serrated, otherwise smooth.
- Tergites I–VI are sub-rectangular in shape, while tergite VII resembles an isosceles trapezoid.

1.1. Pretergite:

- Typically more smooth than the posttergite (if both granular).
- Certain species (e.g., some bothriurids, see below) present a cluster of granules medially.

1.2. Posttergite:

- Typically more granular than the pretergite (if both granular).
- Tergal carinae restricted to the posttergite when present, and may extend beyond the posterior margin in certain taxa.

2. Genital operculum (*pl.* genital opercula):

[L. *operculum*, “cover”, from *operiō*, “to close”]

Anatomical equivalence: ventral of somite X = ventral of mesosomal segment I.

- A suboval, rhomboid or heart-shaped plate; medially fused, or partially or completely separated by a longitudinal suture.

3. Genital papilla (*pl.* genital papillae):

[L. *papilla*, “nipple, teat”; diminutive of *papula*, “pustule, pimple”]

- A pair of small, slender structure mostly concealed by the genital operculum, fluorescent under UV light.
- The terminal tip may be visible in certain taxa without the need to open the genital operculum.
- Unique to males (as a sexually dimorphic character); it is present at all ontogenetic stages.

4. Pectinal plate:

a.k.a. Basal piece.

Anatomical equivalence: pectinal plate + pectines = ventral of somite XI = ventral of mesosomal segment II.

- A subtriangular or sub-rectangular piece between the genital operculum and sternite III, flanked by a pair of pectines.

5. Pectine/pecten (*pl.* pectines, pectens; *adj.* pectinal):

[L. *pecten*, “comb”]

- Colloquially known as the “comb organ” of the scorpion.
- A thin, flexible, compact modified appendage occurring in a pair on the ventral side of prosoma.

- Used to detect substrate-borne vibrations, and the texture and chemical properties of the substrate.

5.1. Lamella (*pl.* lamellas, lamellae; *adj.* lamellar):

[L. *lamella*, “small, thin plate”; diminutive of *lāmina*, “thin plate”]

- The primary part of the pectine which largely dictates its flexibility.
- Typically divided into marginal and median lamellae but the separating suture may be incomplete.
- Often bear setae which vary in density and types (e.g., fluorescent vs. non-fluorescent).

(1) Marginal lamella:

- A successive series of lamellae located externally on the pectine, facing leg IV coxa.
- Often divided into multiple (at least two) sections but usually low in number and hence high in average length.

(2) Median lamella:

- A successive series of lamellae located between the marginal series and pectinal teeth.
- No median lamella between the most distal marginal lamella and its adjacent pectinal teeth.
- Divided into multiple sections and usually higher in number than the marginal lamellae; otherwise fused and fewer.
- May be progressively increasing in number and hence decreasing in length distally.
- Proximal median lamellae may be wider than the marginal lamellae.
- The most distal marginal lamella may be fused with the more proximal median lamella.

(3) Basal lamella:

- A special type of median lamella (the 1st median lamella).
- The term is used when the 1st median lamella is dilated and extended in females of certain taxa (e.g., genus *Parabuthus*).
- Dilation is unique to females (as a sexually dimorphic character) and its presence is ontogenetically independent.

5.2. Pectinal tooth:

- A typically streamlined to suboval structure that always occurs in series arrayed along the internal margin of pectine.
- Varies in number (1–60+; 1 recorded in female *Opisthophthalmus tumas* Ythier, 2023; 62 recorded in male *Parabuthus cimrmani* Kovařík, 2004) and shape across different species
- Sexually dimorphic in many species where only males can be higher in number, relative length and width.
- Bear numerous peg sensilla on the ventrodistal surface; the sensillar area is larger in males and interspecifically variable.

5.3. Fulcrum (*pl.* fulcra):

[L. *fulcrum*, “bedpost, foot of a couch”, from *fulciō*, “to support”]

- A small, rounded or subtriangular structure situated basally between adjacent pectinal teeth when present.
- Connected with and arrayed along the median lamella but separated from it by sutures basally.
- May be absent in some taxa or vary in number.

5.4. Basidens:

- A small sclerite at the base of each pectinal tooth on the dorsal surface of the pectines.

6. Sternite:

[En. “related to sternum”]

Anatomical equivalence: ventral of somites XII–XVI = ventral of mesosoma segments III–VII = sternites III–VII.

- Five visible plates in extant scorpions; the first visible plate is defined as sternite III, hence the last as sternite VII.
- Posterior margins thickened; lateral margins can be serrated or smooth.
- Sternites III–VI are sub-rectangular in shape, while sternite VII resembles an isosceles trapezoid.
- Sternites III–VI are often smooth at least medially, while sternite VII can be highly granular and/or carinate.
- Sternites III–VI bear a pair of spiracles with each located near the lateral margin.

7. Spiracle:

[L. *spīrāculum*, “air hole”, from *spīrō*, “breathe, respire”]

a.k.a. Stigma (*pl.* stigmata).

- Can be slit-like, elliptical, oval, or circular in shape and varies in diameter; peripheral margin may be more sclerotized.

- Each connected with a book lung beneath the cuticular surface.

IV. **Metasoma** (*pl.* metasomas; *adj.* metasomal)

[Gr. μετά (metá), “after, subsequent”; Gr. σῶμα (sôma), “body”]

a.k.a. Postabdomen.

Anatomical equivalence: somites XVII–XXI = metasoma I–V.

- Colloquially known as the “tail” of the scorpion; it is not the true (postnatal) tail as in vertebrates.
- Connecting with the mesosoma anteriorly and telson posteriorly.
- Five highly flexible segments, able to extend forwardly and backwardly, to curve spirally, and to rotate around the basal junction between all segments (as well as that between mesosoma VII and metasoma I).

1. **Metasomal segment:**

- Often increasing in length towards the posteriority, with segment V pronouncedly more elongated.
- Highly variable in relative length, width, height, setation, punctation (pit), granulation, and carination; differences may be intersegmental (between different metasomal segments) or interspecific (i.e., diagnostic).
- Typically, metasoma I has the highest number of carinae (4–5 complete pairs) while metasoma V has the lowest (2–3 pairs, plus one ventromedian carina).

2. **Anal arch:**

- A configuration formed by the ventrodiscal and two laterodiscal margins of metasoma V.
- Accommodates the telson when it flips ventrally, thereby concealing the anus (which bears four anal papillae).

2.1. **Lateral anal lobe:**

- Either referred to the extended laterodiscal margin of metasoma V or the enlarged lobe-like crenulation thereon.

2.2. **Ventral anal lobe:**

- Referred to the enlarged lobe-like crenulation on the ventrodiscal margin of metasoma V and occurs in series.

V. **Telson** (*pl.* telsons; *adj.* telsonic)

[Gr. τέλσον (télson), “end”]

- Colloquially known as the “stinger” of the scorpion.
- Not considered as a true segment/somite (i.e., not a part of the metasoma).
- Connected with metasoma V by membrane, between which situates the anus.

1. **Vesicle** (*pl.* vesicles; *adj.* vesicular):

[L. *vēsīcula*, diminutive of *vēsīca*, “bladder”]

- A suboval (but highly variable) structure with a relatively flattened dorsal surface and an irregular but symmetrical base.
- Contains a pair of venom glands, each located on one side of the vesicle and connected with a venom-duct.
- Varies in relative length, girth, shape and morphosculture; may be setose or barely, granular or smooth, grooved or flat.

2. **Aculeus** (*pl.* aculei; *adj.* aculear):

[L. *aculeus*, “sting”; diminutive of *acus*, “needle”]

- A tapered, sharp-tipped and metallicized extremity of the telson with two venom-duct exits located near the tip.
- Varies in relative length, girth and curvature; often smooth and non-hirsute.
- Appear black under UV light with an obvious boundary between the fluorescent base.

3. **Annular ring:**

- Caused by the constricted circumference at vesicle-aculeus juncture, common in families Scorpiopidae and Euscorpiidae.
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Appendages

I. Chelicera (*pl.* chelicerae; *adj.* cheliceral)

[Gr. χηλή (khēlē), “jawbone” + κέρασ (kéras), “horn”]

Anatomical equivalence: somite III.

- The first visible somite; somites I–II (the preoral clypeolabrum and antenna in other arthropods) are absent in all arachnids.

1. Cheliceral coxa:

- Usually a short, smooth and annular segment that connects with the preoral concavity at one end and chelicera at the other through intersegmental membranes.

2. Cheliceral tibia:

2.1. Cheliceral manus:

- Usually a dorsally convex, smooth and cylindrical segment with a straight internal margin and a curved external margin.
- Setations distributed ventrally to internally, varying in type, relative length, density and coverage.
- There may be one seta present on the external margin.
- May be variegated or not (intersexually and interspecifically variable).

2.2. Cheliceral fixed finger:

- An apically sharp and curved process with denticles (teeth) arrayed along the internal margin; marginal denticles are shorter than the apical denticle.
- Five denticles are defined: distal (apical), subdistal, median, basal, and ventral accessory.
- Median and basal denticles may be fused and form a bicuspid trunk; ventral accessory denticles vary in size and number.

3. Cheliceral tarsus:

a.k.a. Cheliceral movable finger; terminal sclerite.

- A more robust, distally bifurcate (which gives rise to the recognition of two planes, dorsal and ventral) and apically sharp process with denticles arrayed along the internal margin; marginal denticles are shorter than the two apical denticles.
- Six denticles are defined: dorsal distal (apical), ventral distal (apical), subdistal, median, basal, and ventral accessory.
- Denticles are highly variable in size, shape and number; some denticles may be absent.

II. Pedipalp (*pl.* pedipalps; *adj.* pedipalpal)

[L. *pēs*, “foot” + *palpus*, “feeler”]

Anatomical equivalence: somite IV.

1. Trochanter (*pl.* trochanters; *adj.* trochanteral):

[Gr. τροχαντήρ (trokhanṭēr), “process at the head of the thighbone”]

- The most proximal movable segment of pedipalp connected to the pedipalp coxa.
- A rounded or cubic and carinate structure primarily responsible for pedipalp rotation.

2. Femur (*pl.* femurs, femora; *adj.* femoral):

[L. *femur*, “thigh, thighbone”]

- A dorsoventrally flattened segment connected with trochanter.
- Mainly horizontal flexion around the trochanter depending on the proximal angular boundary.
- Highly variable in relative length, width, height, setation, granulation, and carination.
- Either similar in width across its length or progressively widens distally.
- Usually more carinate (stronger, but fewer in number) and granular than patella if such morphosculptures present.

3. Patella (*pl.* patellas, patellae; *adj.* patellar):

[L. *patella*, “kneecap”]

- A dorsoventrally flattened (may be slightly dorsally convex) segment acting as the intermediate between chela and femur which provides great flexibility (flexion) to the pedipalp.
- Greater flexibility is allowed at the prolateral surfaces of two ends, which contributes to the inward movement.
- Highly variable in relative length, width, height, setation, granulation, and carination.
- Prolateral margin often more curved than retrolateral margin; often widened medially or sub-medially.

4. Chela (*pl.* chelae; *adj.* chelal):

[Gr. *χηλή* (khēlē), “pincer-like claw”]

- A specialized structure responsible for numerous functions, including predation, defense, perception, climbing, burrowing, self-cleaning, courtship, etc.
- Essentially homologous with tibia and tarsus in combination, where the specialized fixed finger is homologous with the tibial apophysis in other arachnids (e.g., Thelyphonida).
- Highly variable in relative length, width, height, shape, setation, granulation, carination.
- Both fingers are somewhat curved inwardly, especially distally.

4.1. Tibia (*pl.* tibiae; *adj.* tibial):

[L. *tibia*, “shin bone, leg”]

- A segment that tapers into an elongated and ventrally denticulated process known as the fixed finger.
- Distal surface is hollow, truncated and subtriangular, bearing the tarsus (movable finger) by the membrane.

(1) Manus:

[L. *manus*, “hand”]

- Hypervariant in morphology (relative length, girth, shape, setation, granulation and carination); particularly, for its shape, it can be cubic, rounded, cylindrical, dorsoventrally flattened, or laterally flattened.
- A pair of condyles (*adj.* condylar) are present on the two ends of ventrodistal margin, abutting the basal end of tarsus.

(2) Fixed finger:

a.k.a. Tibial apophysis.

- Highly variable in relative length, width, height, shape, setation, granulation, carination, and finger lobes and denticles.
- Approximately a very slender laminar structure with a keeled dorsal surface and dentate ventral margin.
- Tapers distally; dorsal margin curved downwards distally.

4.2. Tarsus (*pl.* tarsi; *adj.* tarsal):

[Gr. *τάρσος* (tarsós), “flat part of the foot”]

a.k.a. Movable finger.

- Highly variable in relative length, width, height, shape, setation, granulation, carination, and finger lobes and denticles.
- Approximately a very slender triangular tetrahedron with a flat ventral surface and dentate dorsal margin.
- Tapers distally; ventral margin curved upwards distally.

III. Leg

Anatomical equivalence: appendages of somites V–VIII (note: somite IX bears embryonic appendages but then disappears).

- The primary structure responsible for locomotion (particularly rapid locomotion); also for catching the emergent young at birth (in females), perception, digging, and self-cleaning.
- The most slender appendage that is present in four pairs, typically progressively increase in length from leg I–IV (some species may have similar lengths for leg III and IV).
- Always have seven segments, with each segment varies in morphology (e.g., carination) across different taxa.
- Femur to telotarsus are all laterally compressed.
- Segments form four main intersegmental angles: trochanter-femur, femur-patella, patella-(tibia-basitarsus), basitarsus-(telotarsus-apotele). The greatest flexibility is permitted at the femur-patella joint, followed by the patella-tibia joint.

1. Trochanter:

- The basal movable segment of leg responsible for the dramatic movements of leg; allows rotation besides flexion.
- A relative short, somewhat cubic to cylindrical segment that increases in length from trochanter I to IV.

2. Femur:

- Typically the longest leg segment (especially on leg IV) responsible for the extension and direction.
- Moderately flexible but mostly just in an upward folding manner at the trochanter-femur joint.

3. Patella:

- Typically slightly shorter but wider and more robust than femur.
- Very flexible but mostly just in a downward folding manner at the femur-patella joint.

4. Tibia:

- A relatively short segment where setae typically begin to proliferate.
- Very flexible but mostly just in a downward folding manner at the patella-tibia joint.

5. Basitarsus (*pl.* basitarsi):

[En. prefix basi-, from L. *basis*, “base”]

a.k.a. Tarsus; 1st tarsomere.

- Typically similar in length or longer than tibia, and may bear numerous long setae.
- Basitarsus and tibia are aligned and less flexible (only laterally), to bear the ground counterforce in a standing stance.

6. Telotarsus (*pl.* telotarsi):

[En. prefix telo-, from Gr. τέλος (telos), “end”]

a.k.a. Tarsus; metatarsus; 2nd tarsomere.

- A short segment often bearing numerous setae and spinules, serving as the support for the standing stance.
- Very flexible but mostly just in an upward folding manner at the basitarsus-telotarsus joint.

7. Apotele (*pl.* apoteles):

[Probably Gr. prefix ἀπό- (apó-), “away from” + τέλος (telos), “end”]

a.k.a. Pretarsus; posttarsus; transtarsus.

- The shortest and most distal segment of leg comprising a pair of ungues and one dactyl.
- Use for surface gripping and locomotion, but with relatively limited flexibility.

7.1. Ungue (*pl.* ungues):

[L. *ungue*, ablative singular of *unguis*, “nail”]

a.k.a. Claw; lateral claw; tarsal claw.

- A pair of stout, curved and apically metallicized structures, mutually forming a V-shaped configuration (pointing at two directions distally).
- Basally connected with the dactyl by a pair of fused membranes with robust tissues within.
- Can vary in relative length, girth and curvature, potentially diagnostic.

7.2. Dactyl (*pl.* dactyls):

[Gr. δάκτυλος (dáktylos), “finger”]

a.k.a. Pseudonychium; median claw.

- A stout, conical and apically metallicized structure forming a roughly right angle against the telotarsal axis, pointing downwardly.
 - Proximally connected with the telotarsus by a membrane that fills the ventral notch of telotarsus.
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Morphosculpture

I. Granule (*pl.* granules; *adj.* granular, granulated)

[L. *grānulum*, diminutive of *granum*, “grain, seed”]

- A relatively small, sclerotized protrusion that may occur on many surfaces, either presented as an isolated object, forming a linear configuration, or covering an area (or as clusters; a set of granules, collectively termed as “granulation”).
- Surfaces coated with very small granules (relative to the dimensions of a sclerite) are described as “shagreened”.
- Can be rounded and blunt (crenulation), or conical and sharp; probably the precursor of many derived morphosculptures.
- Can form a stridulatory surface with/without ridges, as observed in species *Brachistosternus ehrenbergii* and *Timogenes elegans* (on a restricted area located medially on pretergite, rubbed by the posterior edge of anterior tergite), genera *Androctonus* and *Parabuthus* (from tergite VII to metasoma III, rubbed by telson; potentially also in some *Uroplectes*), *Heteroctenus* and *Jaguajir* (on dorsal surface of pectinal tooth, rubbed against granular surface of sternite III), *Oiclus* (on pedipalp coxa, rubbed by setae on coxapophysis I), *Opisthophthalmus* (underneath the anterior margin of prosoma, rubbed by dorsomedial cheliceral setae), *Scorpio* (on pedipalp coxa, rubbed by granules on coxapophysis I), and subfamilies Heterometrinae (on coxapophysis I, rubbed by setae on pedipalp coxa) and Pandininae (on pedipalp coxa, rubbed by setae on coxapophysis I).

II. Tubercle (*pl.* tubercles; *adj.* tubercled)

[L. *tūberculum*, diminutive of *tuber*, “hump, bump”]

a.k.a. Protuberance.

- An arbitrarily used term but generally referred to any specialized, relatively pronounced granules or lumps.

1. Subaculear tubercle (SAT):

a.k.a. Subaculear tooth.

- A structure located close to and underneath (sub-) the aculeus, on the ventromedial axis of the telson.
- Varies in size (small, enlarged, or elongated), shape (rhomboid, triangular or spiniform) and finer morphosculptures.
- Most commonly observed in families Buthidae, Diplocentridae and Vaejovidae.
- Ecological function unknown.

2. Ocular tubercle:

- A lump bearing the median ocelli that varies in surface texture, height, shape and coverage.
- Finer definitions of perioocular structure in genus *Scorpiops* recently proposed by Tang et al. (2024).

III. Carina (*pl.* carinae; *adj.* carinal, carinate)

[L. *carīna*, “keel”]

a.k.a. Keel; crest; ridge.

- A convex, narrow, linear and sclerotized structure, presumably homologous with granules (i.e., formed by arrayed or entirely fused granules).
- Can be costate (smooth and generally continuous), granular (rough and discrete), and costate-granular (intermediate).
- Those located on pedipalps, prosoma and opisthosoma, and telson can be diagnostic.
- Categorized into different types with definitions vary among authors (omitted here; cf. Tang, 2023); homology of different definitions pending further analysis.
- “Keel” is often used as a more general term that includes both categorized and undefined carinae.
- “Ridge” is more often applied to transverse and marginal keels.

1. Superciliary carina:

[En. “above the eyelid”]

- Keel that surrounds the inner side of median ocellus, occurring in a pair when present.

2. Special configurations:

- Some granules are fused with each other or arrayed in a certain direction but do not form distinct (long) carinae.
- When those short carinae are connected in a certain geometric configuration, they may exhibit a reticulated pattern.
- In certain species, fusion of granules are more random and irregular; they do not form a distinct pattern, but only render the surface an uneven texture.

3. Derived terms:

- **Carinal:** pertaining to the carina; e.g., intercarinal, “between carinae”.
- **Carinate:** with carina; e.g., acarinate (without carina), tricarinate (with three carinae), pentacarinata (with five carinae).

IV. Apophysis (*pl.* apophyses; *adj.* apophyseal)

[Gr. ἀπόφυσις (apóphusis), “offshoot”]

a.k.a. Process.

1. Conical apophysis:

- A specialized sexually dimorphic process known from adult males of some bothriurids.
- Presents on the inner surface of chelal manus, at the base of fixed finger.
- Serves copulatory purpose, used to secure female’s chela during courtship.

2. Patellar apophysis:

a.k.a. Patellar process; internal tubercle.

- A relatively sharp and prominent structure located on the inner/prolateral surface of pedipalp patella.
- Most commonly observed in families Heteroscorpionidae, Hormuridae, Scorpionidae and Scorpipidae.

V. Lattice microstructure

- A new term first defined and documented in genera *Grosphus* and *Lychas* by Lowe & Kovařík (2022), then mentioned in *Scorpiops* by Tang (2022), subsequently illustrated in genera *Isometrus*, *Janalychas*, *Langxie* and *Tityus* by Tang et al. (2023; who also reported its presence in genera *Alayotityus* and *Himalayotityobuthus*); also observed in genus *Chaerilus* (Tang, V., pers. obs.).
- A minuscule, irregularly tessellated (hexagonal or pentagonal in profile) and peripherally raised cell that always occurs in abundance.
- Occur on cuticular surfaces between granules and carinae in most observed genera, but only on granules and carinae in *Alayotityus*.
- Ecological function unknown (cf. Tang et al., 2023: 20).

VI. Depression

- When used in a general sense (cf. “punctuation”, “sulcus” below), refers to any concave surface regardless of their shape.
- More often referred to somewhat triangular, oval or rounded cuticular concavities, or large-area depressions (e.g., dorsal surface of metasomal segments).
- Carapacial anteromedian depression is a common example, which is located anterior to the median ocelli and ends in an anteromedian notch of the carapacial anterior margin when present, often confined by two lateral carinae.

VII. Punctuation (*adj.* punctate)

- A non-penetrated cuticular hole often observed on metasomal intercarinal surfaces.
- A special case of depression which is featured by its small diameter and higher density.
- Compare with “socket”: An annular projection from the cuticle, exhibiting a circular orifice from which a seta originates; may extend considerably from the cuticle base, or may be a small, shallow, rim-like projection situated at the cuticle

base surrounding the extending seta. Some sockets are finely crenulated on their orifice.

VIII. Sulcus (*pl.* sulci)

[L. *sulcus*, “furrow, trench”]

a.k.a. Groove; furrow.

- Any concave, narrow and linear indentation (a special case of depression) that can be smooth or finely granular.
- Usually referred to those present on the carapace and telson; can be diagnostic.
- Compare with “striation”: A shallow, longitudinal indentation on a cuticular region or extending most of a seta or spinule’s shaft length, most prominent basally; occurs in abundance, evenly distributed and semi-parallel.

IX. Margin

a.k.a. Edge.

- A general term referred to any structural boundary, but often denotes those demarcating the transition of two surfaces.
 - Margins can be delineated by carinae, thus appearing costate, granular (crenulated or serrated), or costate-granular.
 - Carapacial anterior margin can be ridged, straight, convex or concave (roughly symmetrical to the medial axis), thus potentially diagnostic. When the concavity is deep, it is termed as the “carapacial anteromedian notch”.
 - Dorsal margin of pedipalp movable finger and ventral margin of pedipalp fixed finger are dentate and vary in shape (i.e., straight or undulate).
-

Other structures

I. Finger lobe & notch

- Occur in combination, with the lobe being smaller than (leaves a gap when the fingers are closed) or equal to the notch.
- May not be a perfect match and can be slightly offset.
- May present only in males (sexually dimorphic) or both sexes (with those of females often being weaker).
- Interpreted as a copulatory structure used to secure female’s pedipalp fingers during courtship; but may also serve to crush the prey.
- Typically ontogenetically variable, only visible at the penultimate or adult instar.
- Interspecifically variable in terms of the size, shape and location (basally to medially).

1. Finger lobe:

a.k.a. Hump.

- Typically on the basal to medial section of pedipalp movable finger dorsal margin, as a semicircular to triangular hump.
- May also present at the distal and proximal end of the finger notch depending on its depth and adjacent geometry.

2. Finger notch:

a.k.a. Recess; scalloping; undulate margin.

- Typically on the basal to medial section of pedipalp fixed finger ventral margin, as a semicircular to triangular concavity.
- May also present at the proximal end of the finger lobe if the distal and proximal (separated by the lobe) dorsal margins are not on the same level (i.e., the proximal dorsal margin may be concave, hence the notch).
- Some species exhibit an extended notch on the ventral margin of pedipalp fixed finger that gradually plateaus distally.

3. “Lobe” and “notch” in other senses:

- The term “lobe” may refer to any dilated and compressed small protrusions (sometimes equals “an enlarged denticle”).
- The term “notch” may refer to any marginal indentation (i.e., emargination), e.g., carapacial anteromedian notch.
- In many scorpionid species, the opposing margins of pedipalp fingers exhibit a zigzag geometry, and those convex, triangular hump may be termed as “lobes” which decrease in size distally.

II. Denticle (*pl.* denticles)

[L. *denticulus*, diminutive of *dēns*, “tooth”]

1. Chelal and cheliceral finger dentitions (denticle tips are highly metallicized):

- Pedipalp finger dentition is often organized in a periodically repeating pattern of linear subrows of median denticles (MDs). Enumeration begins from the most distal subrow (the first subrow).
- MD subrows may seem continuous or discrete, based on the presence/absence of an “obvious” gap between two adjacent subrows or an enlarged proximal MD (MDPE; may appear gradual from the previous ones) within each subrow that marks the start of its subrow, or whether each subrow is slanted outward, forming an imbricated configuration as a whole.
- When all subrows are continuous and similar in size, there is no definitive “subrows” and the MDs form a single row.
- MD series may be highly complex and entirely random (or interlaced), thus not forming any clear linear subrows.
- The denticle (often enlarged) on the extremity of the finger is termed as the “terminal denticle”; those adjacent to it but do not form a subrow (arbitrary, as it is based on the relative length they align) are termed as the “subterminal denticle”.
- Besides the MDs that define the main trajectory, many species are often equipped with additional denticles on both sides.
- Those flanking the MD subrow or MDPE on the inner margin of the finger are termed as the “internal accessory denticle” or “inner accessory denticle” (IAD); those on the outer margin are termed as the “external accessory denticle” (EAD) or “outer accessory denticle” (OAD). Accessory denticles are also called “supernumerary granules”; either of both of them may present or not.
- Both accessory denticles begin near the MDPE, and may proliferate distally in certain taxa. When only a pair of IADs (or EADs) is present, the more external denticle is often located more proximally, flanking the tip of the next subrow.
- An EAD may be difficult to discern from its adjacent MDPE if they are similar in size and they may form a continuous, oblique subrow. Conditions complicate when there are two EADs of similar size with MDPE, and they are identified by the angle they form against the MD subrow (i.e., they constitute a short row angled against the MD subrow, with MDPE being the apex).
- In certain taxa, there may be two parallel “MD” rows that separate distally but fuse proximally into a random complex. The inner row may actually be homologous with IADs and thus is an IAD row.

2. Laterobasal aculear serrations (LAS):

- A row of minute, conical denticles located on each side of the aculeus base, found exclusively in family Vaejovidae.
- Consistently located at the region where the narrowing and darkening of the aculeus occurs.
- Composition and spacing of individual denticles are highly variable, typically smaller and denser basally.
- Number of denticles does not increase with age, but intraspecifically variable and can be asymmetrical on both sides.
- Males of many species tend to exhibit a higher average number than the females (14.6–35.0 %).
- Number of denticles is not consistently correlated with the absolute size of the species.

3. Usage in other general cases:

- Can also be termed as “granule” when referred to the rounded and blunt finger dentition.
- Often also referred to any sharp (and relatively large) carinal granules on (“serrated”) metasomal segments.

III. Spur (*pl.* spurs)

[En. “any protruding part connected at one end”]

1. Tibial spur:

- A small, slender and apically sclerotized process located at the ventrodistal end of leg tibia in some buthids.
- Can be diagnostic given its inconsistent presence across different taxa owing to its ecologically adaptive function.
- Most terrestrial Old World buthids have the tibial spur, while all New World arboreal buthids have lost it.

2. Pedal spur:

a.k.a. Calcar.

- A small, slender and apically sclerotized process located at the ventrodistal end of leg basitarsus.
- Occurs in a pair on the same base, with one pointing prolaterally and the other retrolaterally.
- Only three species are known to lack pedal spurs (Hjelle, 1990: 10).

IV. Membrane (*pl.* membranes)

[L. *membrāna*, “skin or membrane covering parts of the body”; from *membrum*, “member, a part of a whole”]

1. Intersegmental membrane:

- A general term referred to any membrane between two adjacent segments; often refers to those small in surface area.

2. Pleural membrane:

- A specific type of intersegmental membrane that connects the tergites and sternites laterally.
- Highly flexible, crucial for the biological activities of scorpions (e.g., food storage, ecdysis, and pregnancy).

3. Postgenital fold:

- A specific type of intersegmental membrane that connects the genital operculum and pectinal plate.

V. Sensillum (*pl.* sensilla; *adj.* sensillar)

[L. *sensillum*, “sensory receptor”, from *sēnsus*, “perception, feeling”]

1. Seta (*pl.* setae; *adj.* setal):

[L. *sēta*, *saeta*, “bristle, hair”]

- A type of sensilla with elongated shafts articulate in a basal socket with rich taxonomic implications (chaetotaxy), widely distributed on all appendages and body segments.
- Grouped into two general morphological types: (1) macrosetae (or macrochaetes) with thicker, dark, rigid and straight shafts; (2) microsetae (or microchaetes) with thinner, pale and flexible shafts, often curved distally. Stahnke (1971) differentiated the macroseta and trichobothrium: the former being a more robust and rigid seta that basally fills the socket, and the latter being one that articulates in the basal socket.
- Macrosetae are non-fluorescent (Type N) except for a short basal section, while microsetae are all fluorescent (Type F).
- Ultrastructural and electrophysiological evidence indicates that macrosetae are mechanoreceptive, whereas microsetae are both mechano- and chemoreceptive. Tarsal setae respond best to compressional waves and may be hygroreceptive.
- Non-acuminate setae with truncate or coronate (or micropapillate) tips located on pedipalp fingers are reported from pedipalps of some buthid genera: *Alayotityus*, *Barbaracurus*, *Chaneke*, and *Tityopsis*.
- Three types of setae are described in the telson of *Barbaracurus*: (1) macrosetae with very long, non-fluorescent shafts and intermediate diameter areolae; (2) long, pale setae with straight or curved fluorescent shafts, and small areolae; (3) short, pale setae with straight or distally curved fluorescent shafts, and very small areolae.

2. Spinule (*pl.* spinules; *adj.* spinulate):

[L. *spīnula*, diminutive of *spīna*, “thorn”]

a.k.a. Spine.

- Referred to short, rigid spines distributed on the ventral surface of leg tarsi.
- A smooth tapering eruption from the cuticle, forming a point at its extremity, exhibiting various thickness and lengths, and may have minor longitudinal striations or be smooth.
- “Spinule cluster” is a group of spinules formed in a median row, either situated in irregular groups, or in highly concentrated clusters (i.e., “tufts”). These spinules are generally long, thin, either tapering to a point or truncated distally.
- Compare with “**spiniform seta**”: A spinoid seta that is relatively short, large and very thick (a special case of macroseta). Spinules are not innervated and do not carry a mechano- and/or chemoreceptive function, as opposed to most seta.

3. Bristle (*pl.* bristles):

[En. “stiff or coarse hair”]

- Generally equivalent to “seta” but more often applied to arrays of slender seta distributed on leg tarsi that form a “bristle comb” in many psammophilous species.

4. Trichobothrium (*pl.* trichobothria; *adj.* trichobothrial):

[Gr. θρίξ (thríx), “hair” + βοθρίον (bothrion), diminutive of βόθρος (bóthros), “trench, pit”]

- A type of highly specialized setae with long, filamentous, laterally compressed shafts arising from large cup-shaped sockets (socket with cellular, concentric rings (striations) on its wall and a smaller deeper areola located at its center).
- Referred specifically to those occurring on pedipalp fixed finger, manus, patella and femur.
- Experimental and theoretical studies show that trichobothria are adapted for detecting air currents and thus movable (immobile, thick setae that occur along within a trichobothrial area are not trichobothria and often non-fluorescent).
- Nomenclatures for each trichobothrium are complicate, taxa-dependent, and potentially arbitrary, requiring further studies on homology. Generally, some fundamental trichobothria are termed with others defined as “accessory”.
- Two main trichobothrial patterns: (1) **orthobothriotaxy**, Type A (superfamily Buthoidea), B (superfamily Chaeriloidea), C (parvorder Iurida) and D (superfamily Pseudochactoidea); (2) **neobothriotaxy**, Type C with additional trichobothria.
- Type A orthobothriotaxy on pedipalp femur is further categorized into α and β patterns, as well as the following sub-patterns (d = dorsal; prolateral = internal; retrodorsal = dorsoexternal): (1) alignment of d_1 – d_3 points away from (α) or toward (β) retrodorsal carina; (2) alignment of d_3 – d_4 points toward (α) or away from (β) retrodorsal carina; (3) placement of d_2 on prolateral (α) or dorsal (β) surface.

5. Tarsal organ:

- A rarely studied structure that was first reported by Foelix & Schabronath (1983).
- Manifested as small sensory pits on the dorsal surface of leg tarsus (basi- and telotarsi), appearing as slight, oval depressions in the cuticle with two pore openings just inside the cuticular rim.

6. Peg sensillum:

- A type of minute, apically truncate and paddle-shaped chemo-tactile sensillum rising from a socket with a slit-shaped terminal pore clustered in abundance on the ventrodorsal surface of each pectinal tooth (up to 120000 in total per male).
- Hypothesized to be used for acquiring and processing ground-based chemical and textural information, thereby recapitulating learned routes to scorpions’ home burrows.
- May be sexually dimorphic in number and length.

7. Basitarsal compound slit sensillum (BCSS):

- Mechanosensory structures composed of striated, curved, successive slits located at the prodorsal end of basitarsus, forming into a fan-shaped configuration.
- A typical tessellation including hard blocks constituting its main body and soft cuticular membranes covering each crack-shaped slit.
- Can efficiently detect and amplify substrate-borne micro-vibrational signals at a certain frequency range which cause slit deformation.
- Most sensitive to surface Rayleigh waves and crucial for locating the vibration source (requires sensilla on multiple legs).
- Slit sensilla themselves are found on on all segments of the leg, including the coxapophyses of legs I and II and the apotele, mostly concentrated on the lateral surface near the joint, but their functions (except BCSS) remain unknown.

8. Constellation array:

- A compact cluster of small sensilla (constellation-shaped microscopic array of sensilla) located on the subterminal external surface of the fixed finger, with each sensillum bearing a short conical or trichoid process emerging from a small “button-like” areola (Fet et al., 2006a).

- Observed in most families: Belisariidae, Buthidae, Bothriuridae, Caraboctonidae, Chaerilidae, Chactidae, Diplocentridae, Euscorpidae, Hadruridae, Hormuridae, Iuridae, Pseudochactidae, Superstitioniidae, and Vaejovidae.
- Ontogenetically stable in number (1–15, most commonly being 4–7) and not sexually dimorphic in number.
- The lowest absolute maximum intersensillar distance (i.e., array size) is observed in buthids, but no correlation between sizes of array and scorpion is discovered (a small species may have the same size as a much larger species).
- Hypothesized to be chemosensory (olfactory function) but require further confirmation.
- Confirmed to be diagnostic for two lineages of vaejovids (subfamily Smeringurinae and genus *Paravaejovis*), each corresponding to a distinct configuration: two and three sensilla within or near the region defined by four landmark setae.

9. Specialized sensilla associated with pedipalp movable finger denticles:

9.1. Subrow proximal sensillum (SPS):

- Limited to taxa (buthids, chactoid families, and vaejovids) with pedipalp movable finger dentition organized into linear subrows of median denticles (Lowe & Fet, 2024).
- In most of those species, a small socketed sensillum with a short shaft is located at the proximal terminus of each subrow.
- In most cases, SPS are non-fluorescent in buthids and fluorescent in non-buthids.

9.2. Subterminal sensilla (STS):

a.k.a. Cruz-Armas sensilla (when restricted to buthids).

- A pair of sensilla located proximal to terminal denticles.
- Buthid fingers typically have two pairs of Type N STS, a proximal filiform (or lanceolate/ fusiform) pair and a distal spatulate pair; in some taxa the spatulate pair is absent.
- Non-buthid fingers typically have a single Type F STS, similar to the Type F SPS.

9.3. Function:

- Type N sensilla are hypothesized to be mechanoreceptive macrosetae.
- Type F sensilla are hypothesized to be chemo-/mechanoreceptive microsetae.
- Both specialized for detecting close-contact stimuli.

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Selected references

- ACOSTA, L. E., D. M. CANDIDO, E. H. BUCKUP & A. D. BRESCOVIT. 2008. Description of *Zabius gaucho* (Scorpiones, Buthidae), a new species from southern Brazil, with an update about the generic diagnosis. *The Journal of Arachnology*, 36: 491–501.
- ACOSTA, L. E. & E. A. MAURY. 1990. Estridulación en *Timogenes elegans* (Mello-Leitão) (Scorpiones, Bothriuridae). *Boletín de la Sociedad de Biología de Concepción*, 61: 29–37.
- ALEXANDER, A. J. 1958. A note on the evolution of stridulation within the family Scorpionidae. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London*, 133: 391–399.
- BROWNELL, P. & R. D. FARLEY. 1979. Detection of vibrations in sand by tarsal sense organs of the nocturnal scorpion, *Paruroctonus mesaensis*. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, 131 (1): 23–30.

- ESPOSITO, L. A., H. Y. YAMAGUTI, C. A. SOUZA, R. PINTO-DA-ROCHA & L. PRENDINI. 2017. Systematic revision of the neotropical club-tailed scorpions, *Physoctonus*, *Rhopalurus*, and *Troglophopalurus*, revalidation of *Heteroctenus*, and descriptions of two new genera and three new species (Buthidae: Rhopalurusinae). *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History*, 415: 1–134.
- FET, V., M. S. BREWER, M. E. SOLEGLAD & D. P. A. NEFF. 2006a. Constellation array: a new sensory structure in scorpions (Arachnida: Scorpiones). *Boletín de la Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa*, 38: 269–278.
- FET, V., M. E. SOLEGLAD & M. S. BREWER. 2006b. Laterobasal aculear serrations (LAS) in scorpion family Vaejovidae (Scorpiones: Chactoidea). *Euscorpius*, 45: 1–19.
- FET, V., M. E. SOLEGLAD, M. S. BREWER, D. P. A. NEFF & M. L. NORTON. 2006c. Constellation array in scorpion genera *Paruroctonus*, *Smeringurus*, *Vejovoidus*, and *Paravaejovis* (Scorpiones: Vaejovidae). *Euscorpius*, 41: 1–15.
- FOELIX, R. F. & G. MÜLLER-VORHOLT. 1983. The fine structure of scorpion sensory organs. II. Pecten sensilla. *Bulletin of the British Arachnological Society*, 6(2): 68–74.
- FOELIX, R. F. & J. SCHABRONATH. 1983. The fine structure of scorpion sensory organs. I. Tarsal sensilla. *Bulletin of the British Arachnological Society*, 6(2): 53–67.
- GAFFIN, D. D. & BRAD P. BRAYFIELD. 2017. Exploring the chemo-textural familiarity hypothesis for scorpion navigation. *Journal of Arachnology*, 45: 265–270.
- HJELLE, J. T. 1990. Anatomy and Morphology. Pp. 5–30. In: Polis, G. A. (ed.) *The Biology of Scorpions*. California, United States: Stanford University Press.
- KOVAŘÍK, F., G. LOWE, F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ & P. JUST. 2022. The genus *Barbaracurus* in Saudi Arabia (Scorpiones: Buthidae), with description of a new species. *Euscorpius*, 365: 1–26.
- LORIA, S. F. & L. PRENDINI. 2014. Homology of the lateral eyes of Scorpiones: a six-ocellus model. *PLoS ONE*, 9(12): 1–30. [doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0112913](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0112913)
- LOWE, G. & F. KOVAŘÍK. 2022. Reanalysis of *Teruelius* and *Grosphus* (Scorpiones: Buthidae) with descriptions of two new species. *Euscorpius*, 356: 1–105.
- LOWE, G. & V. FET. 2024. A survey of proximal sensilla associated with denticle subrows on scorpion pedipalp fingers (Arachnida: Scorpiones), with observations on scorpion fluorescence. *Euscorpius*, 382: 1–107.
- MONOD, L., M. HARVEY & L. PRENDINI. 2013. Stenotopic *Hormurus* Thorell, 1876 scorpions from the monsoon ecosystems of northern Australia, with a discussion on the evolution of burrowing behaviour in Hormuridae Laurie, 1896. *Revue suisse de Zoologie*, 120 (2): 281–346.
- OCHOA, J. A. & A. A. OJANGUREN-AFFILASTRO. 2007. Systematics and distribution of *Brachistosternus* (*Brachistosternus*) *ehrenbergii* (Gervais, 1841), with the first record of stridulation in this genus *Brachistosternus* (Scorpiones: Bothriuridae). *Studies on Neotropical Fauna and Environment*, 42(1): 61–69.
- PRENDINI, L. 2015. Three new *Uroplectes* (Scorpiones: Buthidae) with punctate metasomal segments from tropical central Africa. *American Museum Novitates*, 3840: 1–32.

- SANTOS-DA-SILVA, A. D. P., L. S. CARVALHO & A. D. BRESOVIT. 2017. Two new species of *Bothriurus* Peters, 1861 (Scorpiones, Bothriuridae) from Northeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa*, 4258(3): 238–256
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & V. FET. 2003a. The scorpion sternum: structure and phylogeny (Scorpiones: Orthosterni). *Euscorpius*, 5: 1–34.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & V. FET. 2003b. High-level systematics and phylogeny of the extant scorpions (Scorpiones: Orthosterni). *Euscorpius*, 11: 1–175.
- SOLEGLAD, M. E. & W. D. SISSOM, 2001. Phylogeny of the family Euscorpiidae Laurie, 1896: a major revision. Pp. 25–111 in Fet, V. & P.A. Selden (eds). *Scorpions 2001. In memoriam Gary A. Polis*. Burnham Beeches, Bucks: British Arachnological Society.
- STAHNKE, H. L. 1970. Scorpion nomenclature and mensuration. *Entomological News*, 81(12): 297–316.
- TANG, V. 2022. A new species of genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from Yunnan Province, China, with a preliminary review on its congeners in Yunnan (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae). *Euscorpius*, 360: 1–45.
- TANG, V. 2023. Description of the adult male *Scorpiops tongtongi* Tang, 2022, with further comments on the genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 in China (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae). *Euscorpius*, 377: 1–52.
- TANG, V., Q.-Q. JIA, & L. LIU. 2023. A new monotypic genus and species from China, *Langxie feti* gen. et sp. n. (Scorpiones: Buthidae). *Euscorpius*, 370: 1–101.
- TANG, V., K.-C. OUYANG, Z.-B. LIU & F. ŠTÁHLAVSKÝ. 2024. Three new species of genus *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 from Tibet, China (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae), with implications for the diagnostic values of qualitative characters. *Euscorpius*, 394: 1–40.
- VACHON, M. 1974. Étude des caractères utilisés pour classer les familles et les genres de Scorpions (Arachnides). 1. La trichobothriotaxie en Arachnologie, Sigles trichobothriax et types de trichobothriotaxie chez les Scorpions. *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris*, (3), 140 (Zool. 104), mai-juin 1973: 857–958.
- WANG, K.-J., J.-Q. ZHANG, L.-P. LIU, D.-B. CHEN, H.-L. SONG, Y.-L. WANG, S.-C. NIU, Z.-W. HAN & L.-Q. REN. 2019. Vibrational receptor of scorpion (*Heterometrus petersii*): the basitarsal compound slit sensilla. *Journal of Bionic Engineering*, 16: 76–87.

Figure 2: Fundamental sternum types illustrating special terminology (external view). Sternum *type 1*: *Pseudochactas ovchinnikovi* (left) and *Mesobuthus caucasicus*. Sternum *type 2*: *Calchas nordmanni* (left) and *Cercophonius squama*.

Scorpion sternum: Soleglad & Fet (2003a: 8)

Soleglad & Fet: Phylogeny of the Extant Scorpions

Figures 1-3: Metasomal segment V, ventral view. **1.** *Pseudochactas ovchinnikovi*, showing paired ventral median carinae. **2.** *Chaerilus petzelskai*, showing Y-shaped terminus of single ventral median carina. **3.** *Bioculus comondae*, showing crescent-shaped ventral transverse carina.

Ventral surface of metasoma V: Soleglad & Fet (2003b: 11)

Cross-section of metasoma I, IV and V: Soleglad & Fet (2003b: 12, 14)

Carina: D, dorsal; DL, dorsal lateral; L, lateral; VL, ventral lateral; VM, ventral median; VMS, ventral median secondary

Fig. 43: Pedipalp chelal carina nomenclature showing 10 fundamental carinae. Diagrammatic perspective, as viewed from the fingers. D1 = Digital; D2 = Subdigital; D3 = Dorsal Secondary; D4 = Dorsal Marginal; D5 = Dorsal Internal; V1 = Ventroexternal; V2 = Ventromedian; V3 = Ventrointernal; E = External Secondary; I = Interomedian.

Chelal carinae: Soleglad & Sissom (2001: 41)

Chelal carinae: Acosta et al. (2008: 496)

Carina: D1, digital; D3, dorsal secondary; D4, dorsal marginal; D5, dorsal internal; I, internomedian; V3, ventrointernal; V1, ventroexternal; E, external secondary; VA, ventral accessory.

Trichobothrial nomenclatures defined by Vachon (1974)

SEM image of trichobothrium: Vachon (1974: 885)

Figure 64: Femur α/β trichobothria pattern of fossil and primitive Recent scorpions (after Soleglad & Fet (2001: Fig. 4), in part). Designations reflect three sub-patterns: trichobothria d_1-d_3 alignment with respect to dorsoexternal carina, trichobothria d_3-d_4 alignment with respect to dorsoexternal carina, and d_2 surface position (dorsal or internal). Arrowheads depict direction of alignment, double arrowheads depict parallel alignment. i = internal surface, d = dorsal surface, e = external surface.

Type A- α and A- β patterns in buthoids: Soleglad & Fet (2003b: 34)

Setae and spinules on the ventral surface of telotarsus: Soleglad & Fet (2003b: 27)

Also visible are the paired tarsal spurs at the juncture between basi- and telotarsi.

Figure 10: Leg tarsus, ventral view. *Setae* and *spinules* from representative Recent scorpion genera. Of particular interest, note the spinule clusters in genera *Superstitionia* and *Hadruroides*; the deep irregular ridges in genus *Hadrurus*; the large limbatic socket surrounding the seta of *Scorpio*; and the fine striations present in both *setae* and *spinules*.

Tarsal setae and spinules: Soleglad & Fet (2003b: 18)

Figures 56-63: Cheliceral fixed finger, ventral aspect. 56. *Compsoscorpium elegans* (after Jeram, 1994a: Text-Fig. 4-E, in part). 57. *Pseudochactas ovchinnikovi*. 58. *Chaerilus variegatus*. 59. *Androctonus bicolor*. 60. *Troglocormus willis*. 61. *Pseudo-uroctonus reddelli*. 62. *Smeringurus grandis*. 63. *Vejovoides longiunguis*. *d* = distal (denticle), *sd* = subdistal, *m* = median, *b* = basal, *va* = ventral accessory.

Cheliceral fixed finger: Soleglad & Fet (2003b: 32)

Constellation array in *Serradigitus gertschi gertschi* showing five sensilla: Fet et al. (2006a: 270)

Constellation array in *Paruroctonus becki* (left) and *Smeringurus vachoni* (right): Fet et al. (2006c: 3, 15)

Sensillum: s, sensilla; Ms, major seta; ms1–3, minor setae 1–3; et, external terminal trichobothrium.

Denticle: OD–1 & 2, outer denticles 1 & 2; MD, distal median denticles.

Laterobasal Aculear Serrations: Fet et al. (2006b: 5)

Figures 6-9: Laterobasal Aculear Serrations (LAS), ventral view of aculeus base. **6.** *Paravaejovis pumilis*, male, Ciudad Constitución, Baja California, Mexico. **7.** *Vejovoidus longiunguis*, female, Viscaino Desert, Baja California, Mexico. **8.** *Paruroctonus boreus*, male, Worland, Wyoming, USA. **9.** *Smeringurus mesaensis*, female, Palo Verde Wash, ABDSP, California, USA.

Wrinkled ventral base: Fet et al. (2006b: 13)

Telson (98) and fixed finger setae (97a) in *Barbaracurus yemenensis*: Kovařík et al. (2022: 22)

Subrow proximal sensilla (above) and subterminal sensilla (below): Lowe & Fet (2024: 71, 73)

Lattice microstructures in *Alayotitus sierramaestrae* Armas, 1973 (left) and *Langxie feti* (right): Tang et al. (2023: 23)

Different types of cuticular surface morphosculptures: Lowe & Fet (2024: 81)

Pedipalp finger lobe & notch: Monod et al. (2013: 293)

Hormurus longimanus (locket, 1995), male (A) and female (B). Abbreviations: blf (basal lobe, fixed finger), bnm (basal notch, movable finger), ml (median lobe), slm (suprabasal lobe, movable finger), snf (suprabasal notch, fixed finger).

Conical apophysis in male bothriurid: Santos-da-Silva et al. (2017: 243)

Bothriurus delmari Santos-da-Silva, Carvahlo & Brescovit, 2017, male (C–D) and female (H–I).